

week after they have been prepared. In order to elucidate the reaction mechanisms, solvent effects, deuterium isotope effects, temperature effects and excess acidity analysis were also performed.

Kinetic isotope effect : From the data in Table 1, solvent isotope effects (k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O}) of 2.01 (0.232 mol dm⁻³) can be calculated. D₂O is a weaker base than water and therefore nucleophilic attack by D₂O in an A-2 mechanism will be less effective than H₂O. However, the substrate will be able to compete with the solvent for a deuteron in D₂O more effectively than for a proton in H₂O and thus concentration of the protonated species will be greater in D₂O than in H₂O and consequently, the rate should be faster in the former. This value is consistent with a fast pre-equilibrium protonation of the substrate¹⁰.

Temperature effect : The entropies (ΔS^\ddagger), enthalpies (ΔH^\ddagger) and free energies (ΔG^\ddagger) of activation were calculated by use of the eqn. (2),

$$k = (k_b T/h) \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R) \exp(-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT) \quad (2)$$

by a least-squares procedure (Table 2). All the values are associated with bimolecular mechanism.

Table 2. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis of desferal in HCl*

[Acid] mol dm ⁻³	E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	Corr. coeff.
0.029	72.6	71.1	-124.0	107.8	0.981
0.058	86.1	82.6	-82.6	107.0	0.987
0.116	79.4	76.9	-97.0	105.6	0.999
0.174	82.6	80.1	-84.0	104.9	0.999
0.232	80.9	78.4	-87.0	104.3	0.999
0.290	72.5	69.4	-112.0	102.6	0.992
1.160	80.3	77.9	-76.0	100.4	0.999

* ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , E_a = kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger = J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Solvent effect : The rate of hydrolysis (HCl = 0.058 mol dm⁻³) of desferal was determined in 12 different organic solvents (60%, v/v) (Table 3). The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The solvatochromic parameters and linear solvation energy relationship by Kamlet *et al.*¹¹ have been applied using multilinear regression analysis (eqn. 3),

$$\log k_\psi = A_0 + a\alpha + b\beta + s\pi^* \quad (3)$$

In eqn. (3), A_0 , a , b and s are (solvent-independent) coefficients characteristic of the process and indicative of its sensitivity to the accompanying solvent properties, α is the hydrogen bond donation (HBD) ability of the solvent, β its hydrogen bond acceptance (HBA) and π^* is its polarity/polarizability parameters. The values of α , β and π^* were taken from literature¹². The results of correlation analysis

Table 3. Observed rate constant (k_ψ 10⁵ s⁻¹) of acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of desferal in the solvent at 55° in 0.058M HCl

Solvent	Solvent % v/v	Mole fraction	k_ψ 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹
Dioxane	10	0.0226	1.62
	60	0.2381	2.24
DMSO	10	0.0272	1.72
	60	0.2751	2.16
EG	10	0.0346	1.90
	60	0.3256	2.37
TMS	10	0.0209	1.86
	60	0.0228	2.29
MeCN	10	0.0366	1.58
	60	0.3394	1.75
MeOH	10	0.0472	1.69
	60	0.4045	2.81
THF	10	0.0239	1.32
	60	0.2491	0.99
Me ₂ CO	10	0.0265	1.20
	60	0.0268	0.95
DMF	10	0.0252	0.98
	60	0.2585	0.51
Propan-1-ol	10	0.0253	1.37
	60	0.2595	1.31
Propan-2-ol	10	0.0251	1.29
	60	0.2590	1.10
EtOH	10	0.0329	1.34
	60	0.3157	1.26

in terms of eqn. (3), a triparametric equation involving α , β and π^* and biparametric equation involving β and π^* are

$$\log k_\psi = -3.72 + [(-2.81 \times 10^{-4})\alpha - 1.40\beta - 0.25\pi^*]$$

$$n = 9 \quad r^2 = 0.28 \quad sd = 0.28$$

$$\log k_\psi = -2.22 + (-2.44\beta - 5.59\pi^*)$$

$$n = 9 \quad r^2 = 0.97 \quad sd = 0.55$$

Salt effect : Table 4 shows the effect of added potassium chloride and lithium perchlorate on the rate of hydrolysis of desferal. It is seen that both the salts showed negligible effect on the rate of hydrolysis. Bunton *et al.*¹³ showed that the anions of high charge density such as chloride hinder only slightly in A-2 mechanism. For an A-1 type mechanism both chlorides and perchlorates assist the hydrolysis significantly. Thus, the data in the Table 4 suggest that the substrate is undergoing reaction by an A-2 pathway.

Excess acidity analysis : This excellent method has been extensively used in recent years for the determination of reaction mechanisms in aqueous mineral acid media¹⁴. Many organic reactions, from decomposition of military explosives RDX¹⁵ to hydrolysis of lactams¹⁶ were studied and analyzed successfully by Cox *et al.* Our previous studies of monohydroxamic acids revealed a remarkable range of structure-reactivity relationships and a wealth of mechanistic

Table 4. Observed pseudo-first order rate constants coefficients for the acidic hydrolysis of desferal in different salt concentrations at 55° in 0.232 M HCl

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	k_{ψ} 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹	
	KCl	LiClO ₄
0	6.33	6.33
0.01	6.73	5.68
0.05	5.98	—
0.10	6.63	6.43

variety⁶⁻⁸. The excess acidity method works by examining plots of $\log k_{\psi} - \log C_{H^+}$ against X , where k_{ψ} are observed rate constants as a function of acidity for the reaction, C_{H^+} is the molar proton concentration and X the excess acidity of the medium; values are given in Cox and Yates¹⁷. If these plots are linear the reaction mechanism is A-1 or A-S_E2, and it curved, A-2. A curvature is obtained. This indicates that the reaction mechanism is not A-1 or A-S_E2. Once a mechanism is identified in this way as being A-2, the species reacting with the protonated substrate at the transition state can be identified by plotting $\log k_{\psi} - \log C_{H^+} - \log a_{H_2O}$ against X (a = molar activity), trying different nucleophile until linearity is achieved¹⁸. Desferal undergoes hydrolysis involving 5 water molecules. At very low acidity (0.029–2.9 mol dm⁻³) excess acidity analysis plot showed scattering, because the values of activity of water are constant. The straight-line with positive slope was obtained in the range 0.58–2.32 mol dm⁻³. The values of X and $\log a_{H_2O}$ were taken from literature¹⁹. Although a knowledge of the protonation constant and ionization ratio with acidity is required but excess acidity treatments overcome many difficulties regarding protonation and activity coefficient assumptions etc.

Mechanism : The available evidence suggests that at low acidity, the hydrolysis of desferal proceed via an A-2 mechanism in which a water molecule is involved in the rate-determining step (Scheme 1). No evidence for a unimolecular pathway, such as changes in activation entropies or solvent isotope effects, was seen for the hydrolysis of desferal in the acidity range studied. The generally accepted mechanism for acid-catalyzed hydroxamic acid hydrolysis involves the initial attack of H₂O on the protonation species to produce a neutral intermediate, that rapidly undergoes N-protonated and breakdown to products. Desferal is a trihydroxamic acid. There are five carbonyl groups present in desferal. First, the carbonyl groups attached to cadaverine part get protonated (Scheme 1). Cadaverine part is more basic due to the presence of amino group. Monoprotonated desferal (SH⁺) is protonated again on the carbonyl oxygen; insofar as the substrate is already

Scheme 1

positively charged, the possibility that this second protonation is rate-determining must be considered. Diprotonated species then undergo nucleophilic attack. Five water molecules are involving in this step. There are two views : (i) synchronous nucleophilic addition of water molecules and a proton switch to the nitrogen, and (ii) nucleophilic attack by water molecule before the proton switch to the nitrogen. According to Guthrie *et al.* these processes are commonly stepwise rather than concerted. Protonation and deprotonation steps are assumed to be fast equilibrium reactions, and the tetrahedral intermediate, once formed, also breaks apart rapidly.

Experimental

Desferal (desferrioxamine mesylate, C₂₅H₄₈N₆O₈·CH₃SO₃H) was obtained as generous gift from Hindustan Ciba Geigy, Mumbai. Common reagents and solvents (commercial) were used without further purification unless otherwise specified. DCl (isotope purity, >95%) and D₂O (isotopic purity, 99.4%) were procured from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai, India.

The kinetic measurements were carried out on a Unicam UV-2-300 spectrophotometer controlled by a Wipro Acerentra computer and fitted with a thermostated cell compartment regulated to ±0.2°. The reaction was monitored by decrease in characteristic absorption of Fe^{III}-hydroxamic complex reported (λ_{max} 520 nm) earlier⁶. The initial concentration of desferal was 7.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³.

Product studies were performed in solutions identical with those used in the kinetic studies except for higher initial concentration of desferal. Products (succinic acid, acetic acid and 5-amino-1-hydroxyaminopentane) were identified by usual organic tests, spectral data and by comparison with commercially available materials. The protonated 5-amino-1-hydroxyaminopentane was converted into cadaverine in higher concentration of hydrochloric acid.

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References

- 1 B A Holmen, M I Tejedor-Tejedor and W H Casey, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 2197, L Gran, *Appl Environ Microbiol*, 1994, **60**, 2132, L Hersman, T Llyod and G Sposito, *Geochim Cosmochim Acta*, 1995, **59**, 3327, B Kurzak, H Kozlowski and E Farkas, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1992, **114**, 169, D E Crowley, C P P Reid and P J Szaniszlo in "Iron Transport in Microbes, Plants and Animals", eds G Winkelmann, D Van der Helm and J B Neilands, VCH, New York, 1987, pp 375-385, B F Matzanke in "Handbook of Microbial Iron Chelators", ed G Winkelmann, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1991, pp 15-65
- 2 M J Miller and F Malouin in "The Development of Iron Chelators for Clinical Use", eds R J Bergeron and G M Brittenham, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1994, Chap 13, Y Hara and M Akiyama, *Inorg Chem*, 1996, **35**, 5173
- 3 V Berdoukas and S J Yawalkar, "Desferal", Ciba-Geigy, Basle, 1994
- 4 M J Miller, *Chem Rev*, 1989, **89**, 1563, A L Crumbliss, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1990, **105**, 155, C Y Ng, S J Rodgers and K N Raymond, *Inorg Chem*, 1989, **28**, 2062, R Kachadourian, A Dellagi, J Laurent, L Bricard, G Kunesch and D Expert, *Biometals*, 1996, **9**, 143, J Ohkanda and A Katoh, *Chem Lett*, 1996, 423, *Rev Heteroatom Chem*, 1998, **18**, 87
- 5 X Hu and G L Boyer, *Anal Chem*, 1996, **68**, 1812
- 6 K K Ghosh and S Ghosh, *J Org Chem*, 1994, **59**, 1369
- 7 K K Ghosh, S K Rajput and K K Krishnani, *J Phys Org Chem*, 1992, **5**, 39
- 8 K K Ghosh, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1997, **36**, 1089, K K Ghosh and S G Tandon, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1989, **62**, 1304
- 9 M Novak, G A Bonham, L K Mohler and K M Peet, *J Org Chem*, 1998, **53**, 3903, D C Berndt and I E Ward, *J Org Chem*, 1976, **41**, 3297
- 10 K K Ghosh and S G Tandon, *React Kinet Catal Lett*, 1991, **45**, 79
- 11 M J Kamlet, J L H Abbound, M H Abraham and R W Taft, *J Org Chem*, 1983, **48**, 2877, and references cited therein
- 12 Y Marcus, *Chem Soc Rev*, 1993, 409, Y Marcus, *J Chem Soc, Perkin Trans 2*, 1994, 1751
- 13 C A Bunton, J H Crabtree and L Robinson, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1968, **90**, 1258
- 14 R A Cox, K S Cheon, S R Keum and E Buncel, *Can J Chem*, 1998, **76**, 896, K S Chenon, R A Cox, S R Keum and E Buncel, *J Chem Soc, Perkin Trans 2*, 1998, 1231, R A Cox, *Can J Chem*, 1997, **75**, 1093, R A Cox, *J Chem Soc, Perkin Trans 2*, 1997, 1743
- 15 R A Cox, *Can J Chem*, 1996, **74**, 1774
- 16 R A Cox, *Can J Chem*, 1998, **76**, 649
- 17 R A Cox and K Yates, *Can J Chem*, 1981, **59**, 2116
- 18 R A Cox, *Acc Chem Res*, 1987, **20**, 27
- 19 R A Cox, *Adv Phys Org Chem*, 2000, **35**, 1